

ELABORATING THE WAYS OF TEACHING THEORETICAL GRAMMAR IN SEMINAR CLASSES BY THE TECHNIQUE 'CONCEPT MAPPING': TYPES OF THE MORPHEMES

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ABSTRACT

The topic of our Graduation Project Work is "Elaborating the ways of teaching Theoretical grammar in seminar classes by the techniques Concept mapping" : Types of the morphemes". Teaching theoretical grammar involves presenting several examples that illustrate a specific concept and expecting students to notice how the concept works from these examples. The main goal of the theoretical grammar teaching method is the retention of grammar concepts, with teachers using techniques that are known to work cognitively and make an impression on students' contextual memory.

The demands of linguistic competence are significantly growing nowadays in the field of linguistics and Theoretical Grammar is believed to be a fundamental subject for enabling the students to achieve their intended future needs more effectively compared to the other linguistic subjects. Theoretical grammar is concerned with language in general rather than with an individual language, as is the study of essential components of any human language. Transformational grammar is one variety of theoretical grammar. Theoretical grammar or syntax is concerned with making completely explicit

the formalisms of grammar, and in providing scientific arguments or explanations in favour of one account of grammar rather than another, in terms of a general theory of human language.

Using the 'Concept mapping' technique in developing communicative abilities is considered an example of CLT activity, it gives a chance to us to observe implementation of all CLT principles in an extended way. During learning process of CLT, students' are hoped to communicate orally and conquer all components of communicative competence and teacher is being motivator, assessor, facilitator, and corrector during students' discussion or

speaking in front of the class. As the motivator I used 'Concept mapping' technique for encouraging peer learning. The term 'peer learning', however, remains abstract. The sense in which we use it here suggests a two-way, reciprocal learning activity. Peer learning should be mutually beneficial and involve the sharing of knowledge, ideas and experience between the participants. It can be described as a way of moving beyond independent to interdependent or mutual learning (Boud, 1988).

Students learn a great deal by explaining their ideas to others and by participating in activities in which they can learn from their peers. They develop skills in organizing and planning learning activities, working collaboratively with others, giving and receiving feedback and evaluating their own learning. Peer learning is becoming an increasingly important part of many courses, and it is being used in a variety of contexts and disciplines in many countries. The potential of peer learning is starting to be realized, but examination of the ways in which it is used in existing courses suggests that practices are often introduced in an ad hoc way, without consideration of their implications. When such practices are used unsystematically, students unfamiliar with this approach become confused about what they are supposed to be doing, they miss opportunities for learning altogether, and fail to develop the skills expected of them. Much peer learning occurs informally without staff involvement, and students who are already effective learners tend to benefit disproportionately when it is left to chance. Formalized peer learning can help students learn effectively. At a time when

university resources are stretched and demands upon staff are increasing, it offers students the opportunity to learn from each other. It gives them considerably more practice than traditional teaching and learning methods in taking responsibility for their own learning and, more generally, learning how to learn. It is not a substitute for teaching and activities designed and conducted by staff members, but an important addition to the repertoire of teaching and learning activities that can enhance the quality of education. It is important to consider who are the 'peers' in peer learning. Generally, peers are other people in a similar situation to each other who do not have a role in that situation as teacher or expert practitioner. They may have considerable experience and expertise or they may have relatively little. They share the status as fellow learners and they are accepted as such. Most importantly, they do not have power over each other by virtue of their position or responsibilities. Throughout the book we will be discussing the role of students who are in the same classes as those from whom they are learning.

The "Concept mapping" is one of the learning strategies to enable students in learning speaking. This strategy is suitable to be applied in a number of students more than 20 people. All students are involved in speaking activities because they can face their partners in asking and answering some questions each other. Collaborative "concept mapping" is a great way for students to step away from their individual perspectives. Groups can do this to review previous work, or it can help them map ideas for projects and assignments. In pre-COVID times,

you may have covered classroom walls with sticky notes and chart paper – now there are many online tools that make it simple to map out connections between ideas. Before applying the ‘concept map’, of course the students are provided the information how to analyze language elements that are being studied, such as formation of types of the morphemes, the ways of dividing bound morphemes into two groups, and so on. By using ‘*concept map*’ strategy in teaching and learning English speaking skills, it can implement and cultivate politeness in English as an example of pragmatic competence because all students can get a turn to speak and be able to use the English politeness expressions continuously so that they are accustomed in using English politeness expressions when they are speaking. Besides being able to cultivate students in using English politeness expressions, students can also be accustomed to hear other people talking or arguing before submitting comments or personal opinion as well. The students can also cooperate well, consider and respect someone opinions, and ask some opinion in polite speech, and always be able to choose appropriate vocabulary (diction) in any situation. There are following advantages of the technique ‘content map’ as it

Concept mapping helps to elicit my students’ thinking and relationships between concepts and ideas. In the most successful cases, concept mapping when used as a strategy with groups, the tasks involved helps to generate deep and

meaningful conversations among students. When used for a specific learning objective, concept mapping works well when there are some constraints on the nodes and the relational links. Specifically, try to limit the number of concepts (nodes) and ask students to elaborate on their relational links. These kinds of approaches require the mastery of competencies across a wide variety of tasks. Students must demonstrate an ability to perform. It is no longer enough to fill in blanks or do scripted activities that may have little relevance outside the classroom. Instead, students need to show that they can actually communicate well enough to perform a real world task. These specialized tasks, examples or demonstrations are the reflection of what she/he has been learning from a communicative course. On the other hand, in my lesson I didn’t restrict my students at all. Since in CLT fluency of much more important than accuracy and language is created by individuals often through trial and error, the same characteristics can be seen in the process of my lesson. The aim is to motivate them to work with the language. I was sure that the speaking activities I have chosen for the learners were interesting and appropriate for their age as one of the distinctive features of CLT choosing tasks suitable for their gender, age, interests and etc .

In my opinion, if we look at the demand today, vocabulary and speech are in the first place, but the pronunciation is also very important. Grammar and translation are important to the classical method, but the traditional method does not ignore it.

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